

Does the visual input matter? Influence of non-driving related tasks on car sickness in an open road setting

Myriam Metzulat^a, Barbara Metz^b, Andreas Landau^c, Alexandra Neukum^d, Wilfried Kunde^e

^a WIVW GmbH; Robert-Bosch-Straße 4, 97209 Veitshöchheim, Germany, Corresponding author: metzulat@wivw.de

^b WIVW GmbH; Robert-Bosch-Straße 4, 97209 Veitshöchheim, Germany, metz@wivw.de

^c WIVW GmbH; Robert-Bosch-Straße 4, 97209 Veitshöchheim, Germany, landau@wivw.de

^d WIVW GmbH; Robert-Bosch-Straße 4, 97209 Veitshöchheim, Germany, neukum@wivw.de

^e University of Würzburg, Department of Psychology (III), Röntgenring 11, 97070 Würzburg, Germany, wilfried.kunde@uni-wuerzburg.de

Abstract— With the development of highly automated driving functions, drivers will no longer be in full charge of the driving task and can instead engage in a variety of non-driving related tasks (NDRTs), such as reading or watching a movie. However, engaging in these tasks increases the risk of experiencing motion sickness in a car. So far, most studies have compared everyday tasks such as reading and watching movies regarding their impact on car sickness. In this on-road driving study, a more theoretical approach was taken and controlled tasks were chosen to compare certain task characteristics regarding their impact on car sickness. In a within subject design, $N = 20$ moderately to severely susceptible participants completed three experimental drives on separate days, each with one task. To induce car sickness, a standardized driving profile including highly dynamic manoeuvres was driven on open roads. Three tasks with different types of visual input were selected: an auditory n-back task, a static visual n-back task, and a dynamic visual task. Participants were instructed to look down at a tablet throughout the drive and not to look up through the windscreen in all conditions. Driving dynamics, task performance and mental workload of the tasks were used as control variables. The effect of the tasks on the occurrence of car sickness was evaluated using subjective misery scale ratings. On average a medium to high level of car sickness could be induced over all trials. The extent of car sickness differed significantly between task conditions. Both visual tasks produced more car sickness than the auditory task, with the visual dynamic task leading to the most severe symptoms. Visual input in NDRTs, particularly moving images, seem to play a crucial role for the occurrence of car sickness. Possible underlying mechanisms are discussed and methodological implications for the use of NDRTs in realistic driving studies to elicit car sickness are derived.

Keywords: car sickness; non-driving-related tasks; visual input; automated driving; driving behaviour; task performance

1. Introduction

Normally, drivers of cars do not experience symptoms of car sickness, but it is a common phenomenon among passengers (Dong et al., 2011; Rolnick & Lubow, 1991), affecting about two-thirds of them (Schmidt et al., 2020). With the introduction of higher levels of automated driving (SAE L3 and up), drivers are relieved of driving-related activities and will thus take over the role of passengers themselves. During automated driving, the driver can thus engage in a variety of non-driving related tasks (NDRTs) like reading, working, watching movies etc. (in L3 only temporarily until a request for control is required, in L4 for longer durations; SAE, 2021). However, the benefits of automated driving might come at the cost of increased likelihood of car sickness, thereby compromising the utility and acceptance of automated driving. Due to the lack of foresight over the vehicle movements and the engagement in NDRTs requiring visual attention away from the driving scene, the risk of experiencing

47 car sickness increases (Diels & Bos, 2016). This paper focusses therefore on NDRTs and their potential
48 to induce car sickness.

49 *1.1 Phenomenon of car sickness*

50 Car sickness is a subtype of motion sickness, which is a natural response to real or apparent movement
51 and also occurs in other forms of transport like e.g., ships or trains (Reason & Brand, 1975; Tyler &
52 Bard, 1949). Typical symptoms are among others dizziness, sleepiness, headache, stomach awareness,
53 salivation, and nausea, up to vomiting (Graybiel et al., 1968; Reason & Brand, 1975). There are several
54 theories about the mechanisms leading to motion sickness with none covering all aspects of the
55 phenomenon. One of the most cited approaches is the theory of sensory conflict and rearrangement
56 (Reason & Brand, 1975), which attributes motion sickness to a discrepancy between different sensory
57 inputs, i.e., the visual and the vestibular system. While the theory of sensory conflict assumes a conflict
58 between real sensory inputs, a more recent version, the neural mismatch theory, assumes a conflict
59 between real and anticipated inputs based on previous experiences (Reason, 1978).

60 *1.2 Driving Behaviour and car sickness*

61 Motion sickness is a typical response to motion that, from an evolutionary standpoint, the human is
62 not accustomed to, such as low-frequency oscillations. O'Hanlon and McCauley (1974) showed in their
63 study using a vertical motion simulator that the motion sickness incidence is highest at a frequency of
64 0.16Hz. Griffin and Newman (2004a) found that the x- and y-axis accelerations in the vehicle contribute
65 significantly more to car sickness at the given frequencies than the z-axis accelerations, because the
66 frequency peaks there lie in the relevant frequency range around 0.1 Hz. A driving profile that includes
67 a lot of acceleration, braking and cornering is therefore more likely to cause car sickness. The ISO 2631
68 standard (ISO, 1997) defines a calculation based on the driving behaviour resulting in the "Motion
69 sickness dose value" (MSDV). This calculation considers the accelerations of the vehicle and provides
70 a value to indicate the incidence of motion sickness. A frequency weighting is applied, which amplifies
71 frequencies below 1 Hz. The calculation comes from the field of shipping, which is why only movements
72 in the vertical direction were originally taken into account. However, as already mentioned, Griffin
73 suggested that for the prediction of car sickness also longitudinal and lateral accelerations have to be
74 considered and showed that the MSDV values in the x- and y-axes are similar when calculated using the
75 frequency weighting in the current standards (Donohew & Griffin, 2004; Griffin & Mills, 2002; Griffin
76 & Newman, 2004a, 2004b). An overall MSDV value taking into account accelerations in all three
77 dimensions can be calculated as shown by Asua et al. (2022).

78 *1.3 Non-driving related tasks and car sickness*

79 In line with the theory of sensory conflict (Reason & Brand, 1975) and of sensory arrangement
80 (Reason, 1978), NDRTs play a crucial role in the development of motion sickness symptoms. While
81 reading during a car ride, as an example, the visual system provides evidence for a static environment,
82 whereas the vestibular system senses accelerations of the car, thus indicating self-movement. This
83 contradictory impression as well as the lack of predictability of upcoming car movements increase the
84 risk of car sickness compared to aligning visual and vestibular perception by looking outside the car
85 window (Griffin & Newman, 2004b; Rolnick & Lubow, 1991). Likewise, further studies have shown
86 that engaging in a visual NDRT leads to more car sickness compared to looking outside (Brietzke et al.,
87 2020, 2021; Jones et al., 2019). Similarly, higher display positions with retained peripheral visual cues
88 of the road ahead and vehicle movement were shown to cause less car sickness compared to lower display
89 positions with reduced visual cues (Kuiper et al., 2018).

90 Besides experimental studies, surveys have also shown that NDRTs such as reading, texting,
91 watching video, playing games, working while looking down were associated with increased car
92 sickness - looking at the road as well as sleeping, on the other hand, are not associated with increased
93 car sickness (Sivak & Schoettle, 2015). In another survey, more than half of the participants stated
94 that visual activities like reading, watching movie, writing, or using a device were likely to induce car
95 sickness in them (Schmidt et al., 2020).

96 In experimental studies, different non-driving related tasks are used to induce car sickness. Reading
97 (e.g., Karjanto et al., 2021; Kremer et al., 2022; Tomzig et al., 2023) and video watching (e.g., Brietzke
98 et al., 2021; Mühlbacher et al., 2020; Schmidt et al., 2019) as naturalistic tasks represent the most
99 common ones. Playing games like e.g., Sudoku puzzle (Talsma et al., 2023) or standardized tasks, e.g.,
100 visual search task are used less frequently (Kuiper et al., 2018).

101 There are only few studies comparing the extent of car sickness between different NDRTs to better
102 understand the underlying mechanisms and those that do mainly use naturalistic NDRTs. Some studies
103 compared the induction of car sickness by reading and video watching (Isu et al., 2014; Morimoto et al.,
104 2008; Ramulu, 2019). Isu et al. (2014) and Morimoto et al. (2008) used in-vehicle displays for video
105 watching and a hand-held book for reading, while Ramulu's study used a hand-held tablet for reading
106 and video watching. Although the studies used different approaches in terms of the positions and devices
107 for both tasks: same (fixed display) or different ones (fixed vs. hand-held), all concluded that reading
108 induces more car sickness than video watching. Furthermore, Schmidt et al. compared three NDRT
109 conditions on the back seats regarding the extent of motion sickness: no NDRT (baseline), video
110 watching on a hand-held tablet on the lap and video watching on a fixed display on eye level. Even
111 though there was a significant effect of video-watching itself on the motion sickness level, there was no
112 significant difference between hand-held and fixed position (Schmidt et al., 2019). In general, NDRTs
113 can be performed on different devices in different positions. Until now, the handheld device is expected
114 to be the most common option for the front passenger seat, as there should be no displays within the
115 driver's field of view, including the front passenger side, that show, for example, video or text that is not
116 relevant to driving, in order to avoid distraction (NHTSA, 2013).

117 Bohrmann et al. (2018) also included reading and video watching in their car sickness test track study
118 as well as a "Who wants to be a millionaire"-quiz and a game, in which obstacles had to be avoided with
119 fast turns, rotations and colour changes. All four tasks were performed on a tablet attached to the vehicle
120 structure. The authors assumed, but did not measure, that watching the video and playing the quiz would
121 be less cognitively demanding, whereas reading and playing the game would require more attention and
122 concentration. In this study, only the pleasantness of tasks and not the actual motion sickness was
123 reported and compared. Reading and gaming were reported more often as unpleasant than video
124 watching and the quiz. Most participants cited the high cognitive demands as the reason, though some
125 felt less distracted from motion sickness due to the low mental demands of video watching and quizzing,
126 and therefore preferred the other two high demand tasks. Other reasons given for discomfort were the
127 driving dynamics and the visual dynamics of the task, i.e. the movements on the display. In the study of
128 Ramulu (2019), the difference in the level of motion sickness between reading and video viewing could
129 also not be explained by perceived mental workload, possibly because it may vary between individuals
130 if high mental demands exacerbate or distract from symptoms, as demonstrated in the study of Bohrmann
131 et al. (2018).

132 However, all these reported tasks differ in a couple of features rendering it impossible to determine
133 which aspect of the tasks is most crucial for car sickness induction. In case of reading and video watching
134 for example, not only the visual input (static images vs. moving images) but also the involvement and
135 cognitive demands differ from one another. Therefore, more controlled tasks including within-task
136 manipulations should be considered, to allow conclusions to be drawn about the importance of specific
137 task characteristics for the occurrence of motion sickness.

138 To the authors' knowledge, there are no studies comparing different artificial or standardized tasks
139 allowing control of performance with regard to the occurrence of car sickness. In the context of
140 automated driving studies, several standardized tasks are used, e.g., to assess the influence on take-over
141 or driving performance (Naujoks et al., 2018). One example is a visual search task, the Surrogate
142 Reference Task (SuRT), where drivers must find a larger target circle which is among same-sized
143 distractor circles (Mattes & Hallén, 2009). The n-back task by Kirchner (1958) is another controlled task
144 which measures cognitive flexibility and working memory (Jaeggi et al., 2010). It is widely used as a
145 distraction task in driving studies (von Janczewski et al., 2021). There are several variations and
146 implementations of the task. The most typical one is that participants are presented with a sequence of
147 stimuli (letters, numbers, or words, etc.) and are required to indicate whether the current stimulus matches
148 the one presented 'n' steps back in the sequence (Owen et al., 2005). As the stimuli can be presented

149 visually or auditorily, the effect of different modalities can be tested, which is also why this task was
150 chosen for the present study.

151 A significant advantage of these controlled tasks over naturalistic tasks is that performance can be
152 measured continuously or at least at the end of task. Thus, task engagement can be checked over the
153 drive as well. It is also of interest if performance and the actual engagement changes when car sickness
154 appears. Some studies have shown that symptoms of motion sickness lead to reduced cognitive
155 performance (Bos, 2015; Dahlman et al., 2009; Smyth et al., 2018) while other studies have found no
156 negative effects on objective performance (Bohrmann et al., 2018; Irmak, De Winkel, et al., 2021).
157 Although not the focus of this paper, it is interesting to consider the relationship between motion sickness
158 and performance on the NDRTs.

159

160 **2. Objectives**

161 As reported above, previous studies on the effect of NDRTs on car sickness only have used one task
162 or when comparing different tasks did so with realistic tasks like reading and video watching. These
163 tasks differ not only in visual input but also in mental demands and actual involvement in the task.
164 Therefore, it is hard to draw any conclusions about the crucial characteristics of the tasks for eliciting
165 car sickness. In this study, a more theoretical approach was taken and controlled performance tasks,
166 which differ in certain task characteristics were chosen. These tasks allow control of actual task
167 performance and hence task involvement. By varying the task characteristics of interest, it is possible
168 to estimate the most relevant sickness related components. The specific research questions are as
169 follows:

- 170 • Does additional visual input in a NDRT on top of the aspect of looking down increase the
171 extent of car sickness to a significant amount?
- 172 • Is there a difference in the level of car sickness between the type of visual input (static vs.
173 dynamic) of NDRTs?

174 Since motion on the screen is considered the most uncomfortable in NDRTs, as mentioned above,
175 the visual dynamic input may cause the most severe car sickness. In line with the theory of sensory
176 conflict, it is assumed that both visual conditions (static and dynamic) induce stronger symptoms than
177 only looking down due to a bigger conflict. The results may also help to find a NDRT that can reliably
178 induce car sickness at a higher level to inspire later studies, for example on possible countermeasures.

179

180 **3. Materials and methods**

181 *3.1 Experimental design*

182 In this on-road driving study, three NDRTs were compared in a within-subject design. Each
183 participant experienced three experimental drives on public roads with a standardized dynamic driving
184 profile on separate days. For ethical reasons, each ride did not last longer than 15 minutes, considering
185 that the dynamic stimulation was rather strong in this study. This is a commonly used duration for car
186 sickness studies with related topics (e.g. Isu et al., 2014; Kuiper et al., 2018; Morimoto et al., 2008). On
187 each trial, a different task was performed during the drive. The order of task conditions was randomized
188 and balanced over participants.

189 As repeated motion sickness stimulations may lead to carryover effects (Irmak, Pool, et al., 2021) or
190 habituation (Reason & Brand, 1975), there was a break of at least two days between the trials.
191 Separating trials by several days is a common method (Kremer et al., 2022; Mühlbacher et al., 2020)
192 because sleep usually makes symptoms disappear (Reason & Brand, 1975), leading to comparable
193 motion sickness responses across different driving sessions (Irmak, Pool, et al., 2021).

194

195 *3.2 Task conditions*

196 For the manipulation of visual input, one task with visual static input and one with visual dynamic
197 input was selected. The static task was a visual n-back task with numbers, in which the stimuli only
198 appeared in the same place and did not cause any movement. Numbers from 1 to 9 were displayed in
199 sequence on a tablet, with each character displayed for 1 s and a blank interval of 10 ms. It was a 2-
200 back task, meaning that a key had to be pressed as quickly as possible when the number displayed two
201 steps before was equal to the number currently displayed. The visual dynamic task was a maze game in
202 which a ball had to be rolled to a target position by balancing the tablet requiring hand-eye coordination
203 (Cabbiegames, 2022). This task was selected to have something constantly moving on the screen. When
204 a level has been solved successfully, the participants should start the next level directly afterwards. The
205 difficulty of the maze increased with each level. Both visual tasks require continuous visual attention
206 and concentration to be completed successfully.

207 As a kind of control condition without visual input an auditory version of the n-back task was chosen.
208 This task was implemented to reflect the aspect of only looking down and thus losing the visual input
209 of the road ahead but still being cognitively involved in a performance task as in the two other
210 conditions. In this case the numbers from 1 to 9 were presented auditorily via headphones with 1.5 s
211 between each announcement of the numbers. Here, it was a 1-back task, which means that participants
212 had to press a key on the tablet as quickly as possible when the same number was announced twice in
213 a row. There is literature showing that the n-back tasks for different modalities, but still with the same
214 number of steps back, differ in terms of performance and underlying cognitive processes (Amon &
215 Bertenthal, 2018). Furthermore, it is almost impossible to implement both modalities with the same
216 timing, as the presentation time in the visual condition can be fixed, while in the auditory condition the
217 actual presentation time is defined by the length of the word and only the gap between the onset times
218 can be defined. Since the goal was not to compare performance in the n-back task between the different
219 modalities, the task was implemented in such a way that it could be solved with comparable effort in
220 both modalities while being driven. An internal pre-test with experts showed that an auditory 2-back
221 task was more difficult and demanding to perform in the car for 15 minutes compared to the visual 2-
222 back task, also considering the possible disturbing driving noise, which is why a 1-back task was chosen.

223 As the question is not whether NDRTs induce motion sickness or not, which has already been shown
224 in several studies (see 1.3), but which kind of task induces motion sickness the most, there is no control
225 condition without task. All tasks were trained for four minutes before the test drive. In all task
226 conditions, including the auditory task, participants were instructed to look down on the tablet
227 throughout the drive and if possible, not to look up through the windscreen.

228

229 *3.3 Apparatus and scenarios*

230 A BMW 5 Series Touring was used as test vehicle. In the experimental drives, the participants were
231 sitting on the passenger seat in all conditions. The seating position was kept constant for all participants.
232 The air conditioning was constantly set to 20 degrees Celsius. For the two n-back tasks a Dell Venue 11
233 Pro 7140 Windows Tablet with an external keypad and for the visual dynamic task a Huawei Media Pad
234 M5 was used. For the two n-back tasks the tablets were placed on the participants' laps whereas in the
235 maze game participants were instructed to hold the tablet in their hands but nevertheless on the same
236 height as the other tablet (few centimetres above the lap). It is therefore assumed that there were
237 comparable downward head tilts in all conditions.

238 The experimental drives took place on open roads in an industrial area surrounding the WIVW GmbH
 239 in Veitshöchheim, Germany. A standardized driving profile was driven. In order to enable the
 240 replicability of the driving dynamics across all drives, certain points were marked on the track where
 241 certain speeds had to be reached in a certain period of time. In the preparation phase of the experiment,
 242 the drivers conducted several training sessions to enable a consistent and reproducible driving style
 243 throughout the experiment. Furthermore, certain behaviours were defined in case a driving manoeuvre
 244 could not be performed as specified due to traffic. The driving manoeuvres were approved by the safety
 245 officer of WIVW GmbH and measures were derived to guarantee the safety of all occupants and other
 246 road users. An experimental drive consisted of 3 rounds of approximately 1.5 km. Each round consisted
 247 of 4 different driving manoeuvres and intermediate sections (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Route for one round with driving manoeuvres (1-4) and MISC queries

248

249 The intermediate sections (a-c) were mainly curves and turns. The driving manoeuvre 1 was driving two
 250 rounds in a roundabout with constant speed. Driving manoeuvre 2 was a stop-and-go scenario with four
 251 accelerations and decelerations into stand still. This was followed by driving manoeuvre 3, which was
 252 also a kind of stop-and-go at higher speeds without decelerating to a standstill. At the end of a round,
 253 two and a half loops were driven in a figure-eight slalom (driving manoeuvre 4). In Fig. 2 you can find
 254 the speed profile for one round over all about 150 driven rounds. The GPS and acceleration data were
 255 recorded using a SILAB® Android application via a Samsung Galaxy A5. Fig. 3 shows the longitudinal
 256 and the lateral accelerations.

Fig. 2. Speed profile (median/5%/95% percentiles) for one round in respect to driven distance

Fig. 3. Longitudinal (a_x) and lateral (a_y) accelerations (median/5%/95% percentiles) for one round in respect to driven distance with relevant manoeuvres for this direction of acceleration highlighted in blue font

257

258 3.4 Participants

259 The participants were recruited via the WIVW test driver panel. $N = 20$ subjects participated in the
 260 study, of these $n = 11$ were female and $n = 9$ male. The mean age was $M = 36.25$ years ($SD = 15.33$,
 261 $Min = 20$, $Max = 61$). The subjects were selected using an online pre-survey based on their susceptibility
 262 to motion sickness, by means of the Motion Sickness Susceptibility Questionnaire Short (MSSQ;
 263 Golding, 1998) and specific questions about susceptibility as a passenger when performing secondary
 264 activities. Moderately to severely susceptible individuals were invited for the study
 265 (mean MSSQ Raw = 30.33, $SD = 10.19$).

266

267

268 *3.5 Dependent Variables*

269 Motion sickness was assessed with two subjective indicators. Before and after the drive, the Motion
 270 Sickness Assessment Questionnaire (MSAQ; Gianaros et al., 2001), which was extended by the "Head"
 271 scale with two items on headache and head pressure, was used for a detailed motion sickness rating. The
 272 original scales are the gastrointestinal (e.g., nauseated, queasy, sick to stomach), central (e.g., disoriented,
 273 dizzy, faint-like), peripheral (e.g., sweaty, hot/warm, clammy), and sopite-related (irritated, drowsy,
 274 uneasy) scales. The misery scale (MISC, see Fig. 4) was used to record motion sickness levels during
 275 the drive (Bos, 2015; Bos et al., 2005).

No problems		0
Some discomfort, but no specific symptoms		1
Discomfort with specific symptoms, but no nausea (dizziness, cold/warm, headache, sweating, blurred vision, yawning, tiredness, burping, stomach/throat awareness...)	vague	2
	little	3
	rather	4
	severe	5
nausea	little	6
	rather	7
	severe	8
	retching	9
vomiting		10

Fig. 4. Used version of the Misery Scale (MISC; Bos, 2015)

276 During the drive, the experimenter asked the participants to vocally express their current MISC level as
 277 well as their current symptoms before and after a manoeuvre (at the marked points in the route, see Fig.
 278 1). The position of the first query per round differed between the first and the two other rounds. The
 279 voice of the participants was recorded throughout the drive.

280 To control whether potential differences between tasks in car sickness might be due to the
 281 involvement of participants into the task and potential other differences, the mental workload,
 282 motivation, and fun were assessed after the drive as control variables. The mental workload was
 283 measured with the NASA-TLX questionnaire for each task (Hart & Staveland, 1988). For motivation
 284 and fun on the task, two additional items were added on the same scale, ranging from 0 = *low* to
 285 10 = *high*. In addition, performance on the tasks was measured. This was done to check that the tasks
 286 were actually performed during the drive and to see if performance changed as car sickness progressed.
 287 For the n-back tasks, reaction time on correct trials as well as the hit and false alarm rate were measured.
 288 For the maze task, the highest level achieved was recorded as a measure of performance.

289 *3.6 Procedure*

290 All participants provided written informed consent at the first trial prior to participation. At the
 291 beginning of each experiment, a detailed baseline motion sickness rating was assessed (pre MSAQ). The
 292 participants were familiarized with the MISC scale and trained to use it. Before the drive, the respective
 293 NDRT for the drive was practiced for 4 minutes. Afterwards, the drive started and lasted 15 minutes
 294 without prior termination. For ethical reasons, a criterion for stopping the drive was set at a value of 8
 295 on the MISC scale (severe nausea). In addition, the drive could be terminated at any time at the request
 296 of the participants without giving reasons or according to the judgement of the experimenter. The
 297 experimental protocol was reviewed and approved by the WIVW ethics officer as well as the data
 298 protection officer. Appropriate measures were defined to ensure the well-being of participants. During
 299 the drive the MISC level was assessed before and after a manoeuvre, approximately every minute. After
 300 the drive, a detailed motion sickness assessment (post MSAQ) on how the participants felt at the end of
 301 the drive and the mental workload assessment for performing the task during the drive was made. Further

302 measurements and a short interview about the ride were realized, which however are not relevant for this
303 paper.

304 3.7 Data Analysis

305 A significance level of $\alpha = .05$ is applied to all statistical tests. For all variables, normal distribution
306 is tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test. If the distribution is normal, repeated measures ANOVAs with post
307 hoc tests are calculated, but if the assumption of normal distribution is violated, non-parametric Friedman
308 tests are used.

309 *Task performance:* To check, if participants really engaged in the tasks during the drive performance
310 measures are considered. For the two n-back tasks the mean reaction time of successful trials, as well as
311 the hit and false alarm rate, are calculated for each participant. The hit rate is the rate of successful trials,
312 i.e. correctly pressed relative to all trials where a response was required. The false alarm rate is the rate
313 of button presses when no response was required relative to all trials where no response was required.
314 For a performance measure in the visual dynamic task, the number of levels successfully completed is
315 divided by the length of the drive, i.e. the number of MISC queries. To check if the tasks were performed,
316 the hit and false alarm rates are compared statistically with a t-test for each participant. If the hit rate is
317 significantly higher than the false alarm rate, this participant will be included. To see if performance
318 changed as car sickness progressed, repeated measures correlations (Bakdash & Marusich, 2017) of the
319 hit rate, false alarm rate, and reaction time in the n-back tasks with the MISC ratings over the drive are
320 calculated. As for the visual dynamic task there is no continuous performance metric and the level
321 become more difficult, a correlation with the MISC-value would not be interpretable. Participants who
322 experience strong motion sickness symptoms and reach the stop criterion will have a shorter duration of
323 drive and therefore, will not get to the more difficult levels, which need more time to solve. Hence, their
324 average level per timepoint will be smaller than for those, who will complete the whole drive. Therefore,
325 no correlation will be calculated for the visual dynamic task.

326 *Mental Workload of tasks:* To check, if the mental workload (NASA-TLX total score) differs between
327 tasks a repeated measures ANOVA with the within-factor task is applied. The items on motivation and
328 fun are compared for the tasks during the drive using Friedman tests due to abnormal distribution.

329 *Driving dynamics over the drive:* To analyse the progression over time, the subjective ratings as well
330 as other indicators are analysed for the timepoints where participants judge their motion sickness during
331 the drive. Dropout in this context means that certain values of this time sequence are missing because
332 the ride was terminated prematurely due to reaching the MISC stop criterion or due to participant request
333 or experimenter judgement. Relevant timepoints for the statistical evaluation of motion sickness
334 comparison over time are the beginning and end of round 1, end of round 2 and 3. The total Motion
335 Sickness Dose Value (MSDV) is calculated based on ISO 2631 from vertical, lateral, and longitudinal
336 accelerations (see 1.2) as described in Asua et al. (2022) to provide a measure of the provocation intensity
337 of the ride. The rotational accelerations were not recorded and neglected for the MSDV calculation as
338 their effect on motion sickness is expected to be insignificant when considering vehicle based
339 accelerations (Papaioannou et al., 2023). Furthermore, rotational filters have a gain around 1 in low
340 frequencies, which is the relevant frequency range for motion sickness and can therefore be neglected
341 (Howarth & Griffin, 2003). To check if the driving dynamics and respectively the intensity of motion
342 sickness provocation differ between tasks for each participant, the MSDV is compared between tasks
343 with Friedman test for the relevant timepoints due to missing normal distribution. As in the first timepoint
344 the car was still standing, the MSDV is compared for the three ends of round.

345 *Total motion sickness level:* To answer the question, if the tasks differ in the extent of car sickness,
346 first the differences between the first rating in vehicle before the start of the drive (pre MISC) and the
347 rating at the end of the drive (post MISC) is calculated separately for each task and participant. The
348 differences between post MSAQ and pre MSAQ is calculated in the same way. A repeated measures
349 ANOVA with the pre-post MISC differences is used to compare the extent of motion sickness between
350 tasks inference statistically. As a further measure of motion sickness, the differences between the tasks
351 in the pre-post MSAQ differences are tested using a repeated measures ANOVA as well. If there is a
352 significant effect, post-hoc tests are calculated.

353 *Progression of car sickness over the drive:* If a participant dropped out the last given MISC value is
 354 used for this participant for the remainder of the drive in the calculation of the mean MISC progression
 355 for the missing values. Hence, each mean MISC score for timepoint and tasks is calculated out of $n = 20$
 356 values. This technique has already been applied in several previous motion sickness studies (Griffin &
 357 Newman, 2004b; Irmak, Pool, et al., 2021; Webb & Griffin, 2003). To test whether motion sickness
 358 differs not only in the pre-post MISC difference but also over the course of the ride, motion sickness
 359 levels are compared for the above mentioned timepoints between tasks using Friedman tests due to the
 360 lack of normal distribution. Last, the duration of the drives is analysed. The duration of the drive is based
 361 on the number of MISC ratings until the end of the drive or until a stop criterion was reached and is
 362 statistically compared using a Friedman test due to missing normal distribution.

363 *Motion sickness symptoms:* To test whether the tasks differed in the type of motion sickness
 364 symptoms, separate Friedman tests are calculated with the pre-post MSAQ differences for each symptom
 365 scale per task due to missing normal distribution. On top of that the symptoms reported by participants
 366 during the ride at each MISC query are categorized. The number of participants experiencing symptoms
 367 of each category during the whole ride is displayed for each task.

368 *Development of car sickness after drive:* The mean development of motion sickness (MISC-ratings)
 369 after the drive is graphically displayed for each task over 15 minutes. The duration of symptoms, which
 370 corresponds to the time until post symptom level equals pre symptom level, is compared between tasks
 371 with a Friedman test due to lacking normal distribution. If the post symptom level does not reach the pre
 372 level the max value of 15 minutes is used. As a MISC value of 1 means “some discomfort but no specific
 373 symptoms” a value of 1 is used as no symptoms left.

374 4. Results

375 *Task performance:* Table 1 shows the mean reaction time, hit and false alarm rate for the visual static
 376 n-back task and the auditory n-back task. It was concluded that all participants actually completed the
 377 tasks during the drive, as the hit rates were significantly higher than the false alarm rates in both tasks
 378 for all participants.

379 **Table 1**

380 Descriptives for n-back performance metrics based on mean values per participant

Metric	auditory n-back				visual n-back			
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
Reaction time (ms)	1069.25	105.27	831.05	1248.69	740.21	98.43	566.76	912.30
Hit rate (%)	83.11	10.62	61	99	65.76	16.50	31	91
False alarm (%)	3.70	1.36	1	6	5.26	5.42	2	27

381 Notes. Hit rate (%) = rate of successful trials (response when response was required), False alarm (%) = rate of
 382 errors (response when no response was required)

384 In the visual dynamic task, the maze game, the mean level score overall participants was $M = 15.25$
 385 ($SD = 5.28$). The mean of the levels completed relative to the length of the drive, which was used to
 386 check if the task was performed over the drive, was $M = 1.10$ ($SD = 0.33$, $Min = 0.54$, $Max = 2.00$). This
 387 means that on average one level was completed between two MISC queries and at least half a level was
 388 completed which is realistic, thus all participants were included.

389 In the visual static n-back task, there was a significant positive relationship between reaction time
 390 ($r = .145$, $df = 287$, $p = .013$) and the MISC ratings over the ride, whereas in the auditory n-back task
 391 there was no correlation ($r = .003$, $df = 300$, n.s.). In both tasks there were significant negative correlations
 392 of MISC with the hit rates (auditory: $r = -.203$, $df = 303$, $p < .001$; visual: $r = -.153$, $df = 300$, $p = .008$).
 393 However, there were no correlations with the false alarm rates (auditory: $r = -.086$, $df = 303$, n.s.; visual:
 394 $r = .041$, $df = 300$, n.s.).

395 *Mental Workload:* The repeated measures ANOVA revealed a significant difference in mental
 396 workload between the tasks [$F(2, 38) = 11.806$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .38$]. The visual static task
 397 ($M = 57.04$, $SD = 13.12$) had the highest values and differed significantly to the auditory task ($M = 42.78$,

398 $SD = 18.83$) with the lowest mental workload ($p = .001$, $M_{Diff} = 14.259$, $95\%-CI[6.761, 21.758]$). The
 399 visual dynamic task had the second highest values ($M = 54.63$, $SD = 12.64$) and only differed
 400 significantly to the auditory task ($p = .001$, $M_{Diff} = 11.852$, $95\%-CI[5.351, 18.352]$) but not to visual static
 401 task. Motivation during the drive did not differ between tasks and was rated very similarly for each task
 402 ($M_{total} = 7.38$, $SD_{total} = 2.10$). Fun experience during the drive differed significantly between tasks
 403 ($\chi^2(2) = 9.081$, $p = .011$, $n = 20$). There was a significantly higher rating ($z = .900$, $p = .004$) in the visual
 404 dynamic task ($M = 5.25$, $SD = 2.43$) compared to the visual static task ($M = 3.35$, $SD = 2.60$). The auditory
 405 task ($M = 4.55$, $SD = 2.59$) did not differ significantly in fun experience to the other tasks and lies in-
 406 between.

407 *Driving dynamics over drive:* The mean MSDV as a measure of driving dynamics and provocation
 408 intensity is shown for each task over the whole drive in Fig.5. The MSDV did not differ significantly at
 409 the end of each round (round 1: $\chi^2(2) = 5.474$, n.s., $n = 19$; round 2: $\chi^2(2) = 3.571$, n.s., $n = 14$; round 3:
 410 $\chi^2(2) = 4.222$, n.s., $n = 9$).

411 **Fig. 5.** Mean MSDV over the ride for each task (error bars: ± 1 SE) on the left y-axis and with the
 dropout-rate (percentage reaching stop criterion) on the right y-axis. On the x-axis are the points of
 MISC queries corresponding to locations in Fig.1 per round.

412 *Total motion sickness level:* Over all drives a mean MISC level of $M = 5.57$ ($SD = 2.30$) and a mean
 413 post MSAQ of $M = 39.88$ ($SD = 17.61$) was recorded. The distribution of pre and post values of MISC
 414 as well as the pre-post MISC differences are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. MISC values before and after the drive and pre-post MISC differences per task

415 The tasks differed significantly in the pre-post MISC-differences [$F(2,38) = 6.058$, $p = .005$, partial
 416 $\eta^2 = .24$] as well as in the pre-post MSAQ differences [$F(2, 38) = 5.124$, $p = .011$, partial $\eta^2 = .21$]. The

417 post-hoc tests for MISC values showed that there was a significant ($p = .001$) difference between the
 418 auditory task and the visual dynamic task ($M_{Diff} = 2.000$, $95\%-CI[0.916, 3.084]$) and a non- significant
 419 difference between the auditory and visual static task ($M_{Diff} = 1.100$, $95\%-CI[-0.123, 2.323]$, $p = .075$)
 420 in the pre-post MISC differences. The pre-post MSAQ differences only differed significantly between
 421 the auditory and visual dynamic task ($p = .002$, $M_{Diff} = -13.482$, $95\%-CI[-21.277, -5.687]$) in the post
 422 hoc tests. In both measures, the visual dynamic task produced the highest increase in car sickness and
 423 the auditory the lowest (see the mean pre-post differences of MISC and MSAQ in table 2).

424 **Table 2**
 425 Descriptives for pre-post motion sickness differences

Task	MISC		MSAQ	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
auditory	3.95	2.14	19.18	15.71
visual dynamic	5.95	1.70	32.66	13.78
visual static	5.05	2.35	27.43	20.67
total	4.98	2.21	26.42	17.59

426

427 *Progression of car sickness over drive:* Figure 7 shows the mean progression of the MISC ratings
 428 over all participants for each task. On the x-axis, the time points of the MISC queries are plotted, which
 429 correspond to the positions in Fig. 1. The bars on the right y-axis show the drop-out rate, meaning the
 430 cumulative percentage of participants having reached the stop criterion at each timepoint. This results in
 431 the final drop-out rates: 50% of the runs in the visual dynamic task, 35% in the visual static task and 15%
 432 in the auditory task.

433

434

435 **Fig. 7.** Mean MISC progression over time with filling up values for dropouts on left y-axis with the
 436 dropout-rate on the right y-axis. On the x-axis are the points of MISC queries corresponding to
 437 locations in Fig.1 per round.

438 The tasks did not differ in the first MISC-rating before starting to drive ($\chi^2(2) = 4.571$, *n.s.*, $n = 20$)
 439 and in the MISC-rating after round one ($\chi^2(2) = 4.056$, *n.s.*, $n = 20$). However, the MISC-ratings after
 440 round 2 differed significantly between tasks ($\chi^2(2) = 8.083$, $p = .018$, $n = 20$), as did the MISC-rating
 441 after round 3 ($\chi^2(2) = 6.862$, $p = .032$, $n = 20$). Post-Hoc tests showed that the significant difference lies
 442 between the auditory and the visual dynamic task with higher levels in the visual dynamic task in both

443 rounds (round 2: $z = .825, p = .009$, round 3: $z = .700, p = .027$). Visual inspection of the data suggests
 444 that there were differences between the visual dynamic and visual static task at the end of round 2 as well
 445 as between visual static and auditory task at the end of round 3, while both comparisons were not
 446 significant ($z = .600, p = .058$ for the former and $z = .700, p = .069$ for the latter comparison).

447 The tasks differed significantly in the duration of the drive ($\chi^2(2) = 6.882, p = .032, n = 20$) with the
 448 visual dynamic task having the shortest duration ($M = 14.7, SD = 4.58$), the auditory task the longest
 449 duration ($M = 17.3, SD = 1.72$) and the visual static task lies in between ($M = 16.4, SD = 3.42$). However,
 450 none of the post-hoc test yielded significant results, there was only a tendency in the difference between
 451 visual dynamic and auditory task ($z = -.600, p = .097$). The duration cannot be interpreted as minutes
 452 because it refers to the number of MISC queries that were location based, not time based.

453 *Motion sickness symptoms:* Figure 8 shows the mean score of each MSAQ scale for the three tasks.
 454 The Friedman tests revealed significant differences for the gastrointestinal scale ($\chi^2(2) = 8.909, p = .012,$
 455 $n = 20$), the central scale ($\chi^2(2) = 7.861, p = .020, n = 20$) and the peripheral scale ($\chi^2(2) = 10.438,$
 456 $p = .005, n = 20$). The post hoc tests showed that for the gastrointestinal ($z = -.925, p = .003$), central
 457 ($z = -.800, p = .011$) and peripheral ($z = -.975, p = .002$) measures there were significantly higher pre-
 458 post differences only for the visual dynamic task compared to the auditory task. The central scale also
 459 differed significantly between visual static and auditory task ($z = -.625, p = .048$). Figure 8 shows the
 460 mean pre-post differences of each MSAQ scale per task.

Fig. 8. MSAQ Scale and Total Score pre-post differences per task (error bars = +/- 1 SE) * $p < .05$

461 The categorization of reported symptoms during the ride revealed the following categories, which
 462 are similar to the MSAQ scales: gastrointestinal, central, sopite, peripheral, head. Furthermore,
 463 symptoms concerning problems with the eyes like blurred vision, eye strain etc. were summarized in
 464 the sixth category named oculomotor symptoms. Figure 9 shows the number of participants who
 465 experienced each symptom category per task.

Fig. 9. Number of participants who reported symptom category during ride

466

467 *Development of car sickness after drive:* Figure 10 shows the mean development of car sickness for
 468 15 minutes after the drive.

Fig. 10. Mean development of car sickness for 15 minutes after drive (error bars = +/- 1 SE)

469 The tasks differed significantly in the duration of symptoms ($\chi^2(2) = 9.186, p = .010, n = 19$). One
 470 participant had to be excluded because of missing data in the visual dynamic condition as the whole
 471 experiment was terminated preliminary due to severe car sickness. The post-hoc tests showed, that there
 472 was a longer duration in visual static task ($M = 11.5$ min, $SD = 4.6, n = 19$) compared to auditory
 473 ($M = 7.9$ min, $SD = 5.5, n = 19$) task ($z = -.763, p = .019$) as well as between the visual dynamic task
 474 ($M = 11.7$ min, $SD = 3.6, n = 19$) compared to the auditory task ($z = -.737, p = .023$).

475 **5. Discussion**

476 This on-road driving study investigated the effect of three NDRTs with different task requirements
477 on the extent of car sickness, i.e., two visual tasks, one with static input and one with dynamic input as
478 well as an auditory task as a kind of control condition for only looking down without additional visual
479 input. In all NDRT conditions symptoms of car sickness appeared, on average a MISC-level of 5.57
480 (severe discomfort up to mild nausea). The visual tasks, especially the one with dynamic input, induced
481 a higher level of car sickness than only looking down. However, this significant difference between the
482 visual dynamic and auditory task only became apparent after a certain driving duration, that is after round
483 2 from 3 possible rounds. To conclude, for a short driving time, for example 5 minutes, differences
484 between tasks may not lead to differences in the severity of car sickness but will become apparent after
485 longer exposure to driving motion. Consistent with these results, in the visual dynamic condition there
486 were more than 3 times as many dropouts (reaching the stop criterion) as in the auditory condition. More
487 than 2 times as many dropouts were registered in the visual static task as in the auditory task. Only in the
488 visual dynamic condition, some participants dropped out already immediately after round 1 and
489 accordingly the duration of the drive was the shortest here.

490 Apparently, the aspect of replacing visual input of the road ahead by visual input of the inside of the
491 car is not as crucial in sickness induction as additional visual input on a display but still sufficient to
492 induce symptoms in susceptible individuals. Although there was no difference in the final measure of
493 car sickness between the visual static and dynamic input, there were descriptively more dropouts and a
494 shorter duration of driving in the visual dynamic condition. Most probably, the difference between the
495 two visual conditions was not significant due to ceiling effects because of the stopping criterion, but there
496 is still a tendency that visual dynamic input is stronger and faster inducing car sickness than visual static
497 input. These results are consistent with the sensory conflict theory that the stronger contradictory sensory
498 inputs (no display, visual static input, visual dynamic input), the stronger the resulting car sickness.

499 In order to check whether the differences in car sickness were due to the different tasks and not to
500 different driving profiles, the MSDV was calculated as a measure of the intensity of the provocation. As
501 it could be shown that the driving behaviour or the provocation intensity did not differ significantly
502 between the tasks, it can be concluded that the different task and not the driving dynamics lead to different
503 levels of car sickness. This implies that predicting or modelling the development of car sickness should
504 take into account not only driving dynamics and individual susceptibility, but also the type of NDRT or
505 visual input.

506 As a further control measure, it was checked for each participant whether the tasks were actually
507 performed. All participants completed the tasks and were therefore included in the analyses. Both n-back
508 tasks showed a significant negative correlation between the MISC score and the hit rate, i.e. the more
509 carsick the less successful. Reaction time was only significantly slower with increasing car sickness in
510 the visual n-back task, but not in the auditory n-back task. A resulting hypothesis to be tested is that the
511 effect of car sickness on reaction time may depend on the modality of the task (visual vs. auditory). There
512 was no correlation with error rates in either task. Thus, the ability to inhibit a response was not affected
513 by car sickness. These results show, that it might depend on type of tasks and performance metric if there
514 are effects of car sickness on cognitive performance, as also shown in previous studies (e.g., Smyth et
515 al., 2018).

516 Mental workload, motivation and fun experience were assessed for all tasks. Motivation during the
517 drive was evaluated the same for all tasks. The two visual tasks had significantly higher mental workload
518 ratings than the auditory task, with the visual static task having the highest ratings. This order differs
519 from the order of car sickness severity, where the visual dynamic task had the highest rating. This
520 suggests that mental workload is not the main difference between the tasks that accounts for the
521 difference in car sickness. In further studies, tasks with the same level of mental workload should be
522 chosen, to really eliminate a confounding factor. Nevertheless, Irmak, De Winkel, et al. (2021) found a
523 significant effect of motion sickness on subjective mental workload. It is also plausible that it is not the
524 level of mental workload that influences the severity of car sickness, but vice versa, the severity of car
525 sickness influences experienced mental workload. This should be tested empirically in further studies.
526 However, as reported above, other studies have failed to find a relationship between mental workload

527 and car sickness (Ramulu, 2019). It should be borne in mind that it likely depends on the individual
528 person whether a high level of mental workload distracts from the symptoms and does not intensify them
529 or exacerbates them (Bohrmann et al., 2018). Fun experience during the drive differed likewise
530 significantly between tasks. There was a significantly higher rating in the visual dynamic task compared
531 to the visual static task with the auditory task in-between. Although the visual-dynamic task induced the
532 most car sickness, participants still enjoyed it the most, implying that fun experiences may not be a
533 protective factor against the occurrence of car sickness.

534 Looking at symptom type, the results showed that the difference in severity of car sickness between
535 tasks was mainly driven by the gastrointestinal, central and peripheral scales. Symptoms reported during
536 the drive corresponded to the symptom categories of the MSAQ with an additional category of
537 oculomotor symptoms relating to symptoms involving the eyes and vision. Interestingly, these symptoms
538 were only reported in the visual static and auditory tasks, but not in the visual dynamic task with the most
539 visual demands (ball tracking) and events. Symptoms lasted the longest after the drive for the visual tasks
540 compared to the auditory tasks. The decrease over time was similar for all tasks (see Fig. 11), making it
541 plausible that tasks with a higher degree of car sickness require more time to return to baseline.

542 Assuming that reading represents a static visual NDRT, as there are static letters instead of moving
543 images and video watching a visual dynamic NDRT because of the moving images, the results of this
544 study first seem inconsistent to the results reported in 1.3 that reading induces more car sickness than
545 video watching (Isu et al., 2014; Morimoto et al., 2008; Ramulu, 2019). However, it has already been
546 shown in other contexts, that eye movements do have an influence on the development of motion sickness
547 and the other way round (Diels et al., 2007; Jäger et al., 2014; Reinprecht, 2019). One must consider,
548 that although there is usually a static image when reading, there are likely more eye movements following
549 the lines than in the visual static task of the presented study, which did not require any eye movements.
550 In this study the visual dynamic task required more eye movements compared to the visual static task as
551 one had to track the moving ball through the maze instead of only looking at a fixed position where
552 numbers appear. These eye movements following the ball might be comparable to those following the
553 lines when reading. For video watching the eye movements probably depend on the kind of video.
554 Nevertheless, one usually processes the visual input with only few saccades. Based on these assumptions
555 and the results of this and previous studies, one possible hypothesis could be that eye movements play a
556 crucial role in triggering car sickness during visual tasks, such that car sickness is more severe when
557 more eye movements are required. To empirically test this hypothesis, it is recommended to likewise
558 record eye movement in future studies on NDRTs in the context of car sickness.

559 What could be seen as a confounding factor is that the implementation of the two n-back tasks was
560 not the same in terms of the number of steps to go back (n). However, this has already been addressed in
561 the Methods section (see 3.2), where it was explained that the focus of the implementation of the tasks
562 was to be able to perform them with a similar amount of effort and concentration for 15 minutes in a
563 moving environment with distracting noise. Therefore, in the auditory condition, a 1-back task was
564 implemented based on an internal pre-test. Although the mental workload resulting from this adaptation
565 was now lower in the auditory condition, the results regarding the mental workload discussed above
566 suggest that the mental workload alone is unlikely to be the crucial difference between the tasks with
567 regard to the occurrence of car sickness.

568 Another possible limitation is the difference between the two visual tasks of having the tablet on the
569 lap in one condition and holding it in the other. However, the posture still was comparable between the
570 two conditions. The tablet was either positioned on the lap or a few centimetres above the lap, with the
571 hands either on the lap or few centimetres above also creating a comparable downward head tilt. In
572 addition, the tablet was light, so no great muscular effort was required to hold the tablet, which makes it
573 unlikely that discomfort appeared, which could have influenced the extent of car sickness. The authors
574 are not aware of any studies showing that arm biofeedback alone influences motion sickness. The study
575 by Schmidt et al. (2019) cited above (see 1.3) also found no significant difference regarding car sickness
576 between watching videos on a handheld tablet on lap and a fixed display. Therefore, the authors assume
577 that the confounding effect of holding the tablet or not on motion sickness alone is not significant.
578 However, the aspect that the visual tasks differed not only in terms of visual input, but also in terms of
579 motor responses is more critical and should be taken into account as a limitation when interpreting the

580 results. While the visual static task only required pressing a button with the finger, the visual dynamic
581 task required dynamic hand or arm movements. In some cases, participants also moved their upper body
582 or head. It might be that this difference between the tasks has a confounding effect on the results. At least
583 there is evidence that there is an influence of head tilt on motion sickness (Brietzke et al., 2020; Wada &
584 Yoshida, 2016). Furthermore, studies exist, which focus on the reduction of upper body and head
585 movement to mitigate the development of car sickness (e.g., Kremer et al., 2022). It is therefore
586 recommended to include in future studies a visual dynamic condition without further body movement as
587 well as one with body movement to be able to separate the effect of additional dynamic movement to
588 dynamic visual input.

589

590 6. Conclusions

591 To conclude, the visual input of tasks matters for the induction of car sickness. Tasks with additional
592 visual input, compared to just looking down and not seeing the road ahead, lead to more severe car
593 sickness symptoms. As far as the type of visual input is concerned, dynamic input, i.e. moving images,
594 induces sickness faster and to a greater extent than static input. As the required visual demands (tracking
595 a moving object vs. looking at a fixed position) were different, it is recommended that further studies
596 record eye movements to draw conclusions about the importance of eye movements in inducing car
597 sickness. If a moderate to high level of car sickness is required (e.g., to efficiently test countermeasures)
598 it can be recommended based on these study results to use visual tasks instead of only looking down in
599 combination with dynamic driving manoeuvres in longitudinal and lateral direction. Visual tasks with
600 dynamic input and hand movements are recommended if even stronger car sickness is to be produced
601 and especially in a short time. Nevertheless, if only mild to moderate symptoms of car sickness are
602 required looking down without visual input is still sufficient for severely susceptible participants. Future
603 studies could verify these results with a more natural driving style and different susceptibilities to car
604 sickness.

605

606 **Author contributions:** Myriam Metzulat: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis,
607 Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation. Barbara Metz: Conceptualization, Writing -
608 Review & Editing, Project administration. Andreas Landau: Data curation. Alexandra Neukum:
609 Funding acquisition. Wilfried Kunde: Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

610

611 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

612

613 **Acknowledgements:** This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
614 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006664. The sole responsibility of
615 this publication lies with the authors. Neither the European Commission nor CINEA – in its capacity
616 of Granting Authority – can be made responsible for any use that may be made of the information this
617 document contains. The authors would like to thank all partners within Hi-Drive for their cooperation
618 and valuable contribution as well as Linda Haas for her support in data collection and experiment
619 preparation.

620

621 **Funding:** This project was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
622 program under grant agreement no. 101006664.

623

624

625

626

627

- 629 Amon, M. J., & Bertenthal, B. I. (2018). Auditory Versus Visual Stimulus Effects on Cognitive
630 Performance During the N-back Task. *CogSci*.
- 631 Asua, E., Gutiérrez-Zaballa, J., Mata-Carballeira, O., Ruiz, J. A., & del Campo, I. (2022). Analysis of
632 the motion sickness and the lack of comfort in car passengers. *Applied Sciences*, *12*(8), 3717.
- 633 Bakdash, J. Z., & Marusich, L. R. (2017). Repeated measures correlation. *Front Psychol*, *8*, 252904.
- 634 Bohrmann, D., Lehnert, K., Scholly, U., & Bengler, K. (2018). *Kinetosis as a Challenge of Future*
635 *Mobility Concepts and Highly Automated Vehicles*. Paper presented at the 27th Aachen
636 Colloquium Automobile and Engine Technology, Aachen.
- 637 Bos, J. E. (2015). Less sickness with more motion and/or mental distraction. *J Vestib Res*, *25*(1), 23-
638 33. <https://doi.org/10.3233/VES-150541>
- 639 Bos, J. E., MacKinnon, S. N., & Patterson, A. (2005). Motion sickness symptoms in a ship motion
640 simulator: effects of inside, outside, and no view. *Aviat Space Environ Med*, *76*(12), 1111-
641 1118.
- 642 Brietzke, A., Pham Xuan, R., Dettmann, A., & Bullinger-Hoffmann, A. (2020). Head motion as
643 indicator for visual anticipation in the context of car sickness. *Preprint*.
- 644 Brietzke, A., Pham Xuan, R., Dettmann, A., & Bullinger-Hoffmann, A. (2021). Influence of dynamic
645 stimulation, visual perception and individual susceptibility to car sickness during controlled
646 stop-and-go driving. *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen*, *85*(1). [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10010-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10010-021-00441-6)
647 [021-00441-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10010-021-00441-6)
- 648 Cabbiegames. (2022). *Classic Labyrinth 3d Maze*. Retrieved from
649 <http://www.classiclabyrinth.com/index.html>. Accessed February 9, 2023
- 650 Dahlman, J., Sjors, A., Lindstrom, J., Ledin, T., & Falkmer, T. (2009). Performance and autonomic
651 responses during motion sickness. *Hum Factors*, *51*(1), 56-66.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720809332848>
- 653 Diels, C., & Bos, J. E. (2016). Self-driving carsickness. *Appl Ergon*, *53 Pt B*, 374-382.
654 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2015.09.009>
- 655 Diels, C., Ukai, K., & Howarth, P. A. (2007). Visually induced motion sickness with radial displays:
656 effects of gaze angle and fixation. *Aviat Space Environ Med*, *78*(7), 659-665.
- 657 Dong, X., Yoshida, K., & Stoffregen, T. A. (2011). Control of a virtual vehicle influences postural
658 activity and motion sickness. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied*, *17*(2), 128.
- 659 Donohew, B. E., & Griffin, M. J. (2004). Motion sickness: effect of the frequency of lateral
660 oscillation. *Aviat Space Environ Med*, *75*(8), 649-656.
- 661 Gianaros, P. J., Muth, E. R., Mordkoff, J. T., Levine, M. E., & Stern, R. M. (2001). A questionnaire for
662 the assessment of the multiple dimensions of motion sickness. *Aviat Space Environ Med*,
663 *72*(2), 115-119.
- 664 Golding, J. F. (1998). Motion sickness susceptibility questionnaire revised and its relationship to other
665 forms of sickness. *Brain Res Bull*, *47*(5), 507-516.
- 666 Graybiel, A., Wood, C. D., Miller, E. F., & Cramer, D. B. (1968). Diagnostic criteria for grading the
667 severity of acute motion sickness. *Aerosp Med*, *39*(5), 453-455.
- 668 Griffin, M. J., & Mills, K. L. (2002). Effect of frequency and direction of horizontal oscillation on
669 motion sickness. *Aviat Space Environ Med*, *73*(6), 537-543.
- 670 Griffin, M. J., & Newman, M. M. (2004a). An experimental study of low-frequency motion in cars.
671 *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part D: Automobile Engineering*,
672 *218*(1), pp. 16-24.
- 673 Griffin, M. J., & Newman, M. M. (2004b). Visual field effects on motion sickness in cars. *Aviat Space*
674 *Environ Med*, *75*(9), 739-748.
- 675 Hart, S. G., & Staveland, L. E. (1988). Development of NASA-TLX (Task Load Index): Results of
676 empirical and theoretical research. In *Advances in psychology* (Vol. 52, pp. 139-183).
- 677 Howarth, H. V., & Griffin, M. J. (2003). Effect of roll oscillation frequency on motion sickness. *Aviat*
678 *Space Environ Med*, *74*(4), 326-331.
- 679 Irmak, T., De Winkel, K., Pattanayak, A., & Happee, R. (2021). Motion sickness, motivation,
680 workload and task performance in automate d vehicles. *Comfort congress 2021 Proceedings*.

- 681 Irmak, T., Pool, D. M., & Happee, R. (2021). Objective and subjective responses to motion sickness:
682 the group and the individual. *Exp Brain Res*, 239(2), 515-531.
- 683 ISO. (1997). ISO 2631-1:1997: Mechanical vibration and shock - Evaluation of human exposure to
684 whole-body vibration. International Organization for Standardization.
685 <https://www.iso.org/standard/7612.html>
- 686 Isu, N., Hasegawa, T., Takeuchi, I., & Morimoto, A. (2014). Quantitative analysis of time-course
687 development of motion sickness caused by in-vehicle video watching. *Displays*, 35(2), 90-97.
- 688 Jaeggi, S. M., Buschkuhl, M., Perrig, W. J., & Meier, B. (2010). The concurrent validity of the N-
689 back task as a working memory measure. *Memory*, 18(4), 394-412.
- 690 Jäger, M., Gruber, N., Müri, R., Mosimann, U. P., & Nef, T. (2014). Manipulations to reduce
691 simulator-related transient adverse health effects during simulated driving. *Med Biol Eng*
692 *Comput*, 52, 601-610.
- 693 von Janczewski, N., Wittmann, J., Engeln, A., Baumann, M., & Krauß, L. (2021). A meta-analysis of
694 the n-back task while driving and its effects on cognitive workload. *Transportation research*
695 *part F: traffic psychology and behaviour*, 76, 269-285.
- 696 Jones, M. L., Le, V. C., Ebert, S. M., Sienko, K. H., Reed, M. P., & Sayer, J. R. (2019). Motion
697 sickness in passenger vehicles during test track operations. *Ergonomics*, 62(10), 1357-1371.
- 698 Karjanto, J., Yusof, N. M., Hassan, M. Z., Terken, J., Delbressine, F., & Rauterberg, M. (2021). An on-
699 road study in mitigating motion sickness when reading in automated driving. *Journal of*
700 *Human University Natural Sciences*, 48(3).
- 701 Kremer, C., Tomzig, M., Merkel, N., & Neukum, A. (2022). Using Active Seat Belt Retractions to
702 Mitigate Motion Sickness in Automated Driving. *Vehicles*, 4(3), 825-842.
- 703 Kuiper, O. X., Bos, J. E., & Diels, C. (2018). Looking forward: In-vehicle auxiliary display
704 positioning affects carsickness. *Appl Ergon*, 68, 169-175.
705 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2017.11.002>
- 706 Mattes, S., & Hallén, A. (2009). Surrogate distraction measurement techniques: The lane change test.
707 *Driver distraction: Theory, effects, and mitigation*, 107-121.
- 708 Morimoto, A., Isu, N., Ioku, D., Asano, H., Kawai, A., & Masui, F. (2008). Effects of reading books
709 and watching movies on inducement of car sickness. *Proceedings of the FISITA 2008 World*
710 *Automotive Congress*, Munich, Germany,
- 711 Mühlbacher, D., Tomzig, M., Reinmüller, K., & Rittger, L. (2020). Methodological Considerations
712 Concerning Motion Sickness Investigations during Automated Driving. *Information*, 11(5),
713 265.
- 714 Naujoks, F., Befelein, D., Wiedemann, K., & Neukum, A. (2018). A review of non-driving-related
715 tasks used in studies on automated driving. *Proceedings of the AHFE 2017 International*
716 *Conference on Human Factors in Transportation*, Los Angeles, California, USA, pp. 525-
717 537.
- 718 NHTSA (2013). Visual-manual NHTSA driver distraction guidelines for in-vehicle electronic devices.
719 *Washington, DC Natl. Highw. Traffic Saf. Adm. (NHTSA), Dep. Transp.*, 78(81).
- 720 O'Hanlon, J. F., & McCauley, M. E. (1974). Motion sickness incidence as a function of the frequency
721 and acceleration of vertical sinusoidal motion. *Aerosp Med*, 45(4), 366-369.
- 722 Owen, A. M., McMillan, K. M., Laird, A. R., & Bullmore, E. (2005). N-back working memory
723 paradigm: A meta-analysis of normative functional neuroimaging studies. *Human brain*
724 *mapping*, 25(1), 46-59.
- 725 Papaioannou, G., Desai, R., & Happee, R. (2023). The impact of body and head dynamics on motion
726 comfort assessment. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.03608*.
- 727 Ramulu, S. H. S. (2019). Relationship of Motion Sickness with Mental Demand and Cold Sweating.
728 Master's Thesis, Eindhoven University of Technology, Netherlands.
729 [https://research.tue.nl/en/studentTheses/relationship-of-motion-sickness-with-mental-](https://research.tue.nl/en/studentTheses/relationship-of-motion-sickness-with-mental-demand-and-cold-sweat)
730 [demand-and-cold-sweat](https://research.tue.nl/en/studentTheses/relationship-of-motion-sickness-with-mental-demand-and-cold-sweat)
- 731 Reason, J. T. (1978). Motion sickness adaptation: a neural mismatch model. *Journal of the Royal*
732 *Society of Medicine*, 71(11), 819-829.
- 733 Reason, J. T., & Brand, J. J. (1975). *Motion sickness*. Academic Press.

- 734 Reinprecht, K., Zellnig, P., Muhrer, E. (2019). *Was tun, wenn das Auto mich fährt?-Auswirkungen von*
735 *Reiseübelkeit auf das Blickverhalten*. Poster presented at the 3. Kongress Fachgruppe
736 Verkehrspsychologie der DGPs 2019, Saarbrücken, Germany.
- 737 Rolnick, A., & Lubow, R. E. (1991). Why is the driver rarely motion sick? The role of controllability
738 in motion sickness. *Ergonomics*, 34(7), 867-879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139108964831>
- 739 SAE. (2021). J3016: Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for
740 On-Road Motor Vehicles. *SAE International/ISO*.
- 741 Schmidt, E., Emmermann, B., Venrooij, J., & Reinprecht, K. (2019). Occurrence of motion sickness
742 during highway and inner-city drives. *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics*
743 *Society Europe*.
- 744 Schmidt, E. A., Kuiper, O. X., Wolter, S., Diels, C., & Bos, J. E. (2020). An international survey on
745 the incidence and modulating factors of carsickness. *Transportation research part F: traffic*
746 *psychology and behaviour*, 71, 76-87.
- 747 Sivak, M., & Schoettle, B. (2015). *Motion Sickness in Self Driving Vehicles*. Report No. UMTRI-
748 2015-12, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Transportation Research Institute.
- 749 Smyth, J., Jennings, P., Mouzakitis, A., & Birrell, S. (2018). Too sick to drive: How motion sickness
750 severity impacts human performance. In *2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent*
751 *Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 1787-1793, IEEE.
- 752 Talsma, T. M., Hassanain, O., Happee, R., & de Winkel, K. N. (2023). Validation of a moving base
753 driving simulator for motion sickness research. *Appl Ergon*, 106, 103897.
- 754 Tomzig, M., Schoemig, N., Wehner, T., Marberger, C., Otto, H., Schulz, M., Kenar, E., & Schultz, A.
755 (2023). How to Make Reading in Fully Automated Vehicles a Better Experience? Effects of
756 Active Seat Belt Retractions and a 2-Step Driving Profile on Subjective Motion Sickness,
757 Ride Comfort and Acceptance. *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on*
758 *Automotive User Interfaces and Interactive Vehicular Applications*, Ingolstadt, Germany,
759 pp. 11-21. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3580585.3607160>
- 760 Tyler, D. B., & Bard, P. (1949). Motion sickness. *Physiol Rev*, 29(4), 311-369.
761 <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.1949.29.4.311>
- 762 Wada, T., & Yoshida, K. (2016). Effect of passengers' active head tilt and opening/closure of eyes on
763 motion sickness in lateral acceleration environment of cars. *Ergonomics*, 59(8), 1050-1059.
764 <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140139.2015.1109713>
- 765 Webb, N. A., & Griffin, M. J. (2003). Eye movement, vection, and motion sickness with foveal and
766 peripheral vision. *Aviat Space Environ Med*, 74(6 Pt 1), 622-625.